
Problem or issue

Clinical coding, and more generally electronic health records, can be used for research without best practice and without consideration of the type and quality of the data source. Furthermore, many tools and resources are readily available, but not compiled as an easy-to-use referable source, thus often missed.

What is already known

There are several methodologies, and tools to implement these methodologies, through which clinical concepts are categorised, though these are not necessarily performed using best practices or easily accessible to researchers.

What this paper adds

Based on our perspectives gained from the Research Support Facility for AI for Multiple Long-Term Conditions (MLTC) and our wider expertise in processing health data for research, we have provided methodologies informed by domain-specific and data science best practices, benchmarked by clinician input and MLTC literature. Additionally, our manuscript covers challenges around overprescribing, initiatives to address related challenges, suggests potential improvements to current practices in coding clinical data, and discusses legacy and future initiatives. We also examine the importance of data quality in health records and the data source selection processes, which can often be overlooked despite playing a crucial role in validity of MLTC research.

From data source to generating code lists: best practices and resources in multiple long-term conditions research

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Abstract

Access to health data, of good enough volume and quality, is central to our understanding of multiple long-term conditions (MLTCs) and how to treat them. There is a rise in the use of health data for cohort selection using clinical codes, with the potential to advance areas of MLTC treatment and polypharmacy research. In this narrative review, we have examined literature with published methodologies to discuss current understanding and potential challenges around coding of clinical data, selection of data sources (e.g. electronic health records) and validity of the decision making process. We include a methodology framework and suggested best practices in developing drug lists with clinician input. We provide an extensive list of resources to assist MLTC researchers to create or access pre-existing code lists, prioritising re-usability and transparency in MLTC cohort selection for specific drug treatments. Sharing best practice guidelines and agreeing on standards can help this research field move towards having a unified approach to structuring and coding clinical information, with the ultimate goal being more accurate and effective clinical decision making.

Keywords: code lists, clinical coding, multiple long-term conditions, polypharmacy, health data, data quality, data standardisation

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1. Background

Accessing healthcare data for research studies is vital to improve the lives of patients [1, 2]. How healthcare data is recorded and structured largely depends on its primary use case, the software system used to host it, and the healthcare professionals responsible for recording it.

A large volume of health data, routinely collected electronic health records (EHRs), are primarily observational not experimental, i.e. they were not recorded with the intention of research. Therefore, the downstream processing and evaluation of these datasets, for the purpose of high quality research, is challenging. These EHRs are subject to miscodings, sub-optimal formatting and lack of standardisation, all resulting in challenges to their initial interpretation and subsequent downstream analyses. These limitations affect both research integrity and how EHRs are used in healthcare settings for patient care, where all relevant clinical information is summarised in interoperable software systems such as Vision, EMIS and SystemOne[3].

Multiple long-term conditions (MLTCs), commonly defined as two or more long-term health conditions [1, 4], are becoming increasingly prevalent in proportion to the continually rising life expectancy [5]. People living with MLTCs have greater medical and social care needs and are at greater risk of worsening mental health conditions, unexpected and longer hospital admissions, mortality and reduced quality of life [6, 5, 7, 8].

This, alongside polypharmacy, results in higher levels of resource utilisation, healthcare costs and burden to health and social care providers [9, 10, 11, 1]. These challenging health outcomes motivate the study of the epidemiology of MLTCs and accompanying polypharmacy effects. With multimodal clinical data at a population scale, this requires best practices in clinical coding and standardised research methodologies to avoid misleading outputs and facilitate comparison of study results. The research community ultimately aims to use these datasets in the development of early clinical interventions to optimise individual patient outcomes and improve quality of life. MLTC studies in particular are challenging to undertake due to the differing classifications of diseases and treatments and the complexity of interactions between multiple condition and drug trajectories.

A strategic programme has been funded by NIHR to investigate these challenges. In the AI for Multiple Long-term Conditions (AIM) programme [12], AI methods combine with healthcare and social science expertise to advance our understanding of MLTCs and polypharmacy. Within this AIM

programme, a multi-disciplinary Research Support Facility (RSF)[13] was funded to develop and promote data standards and research best practices, whilst engaging collaboratively with researchers, patients and the public on the topic of MLTC research. Drug code lists relating to MLTC treatments were identified as particularly important to enable reproducible creation of large cohorts with overlapping condition treatments. The RSF has focused on developing solutions to common research workflow bottlenecks, with the development of standardised drug code lists using transparent methodologies being an example.

In this review, we summarise key considerations, challenges and potential solutions when using EHR data to study MLTCs and health conditions more generally. We begin by reviewing the challenges in defining MLTCs, crucial to the design of a research study. We reflect on the importance of choosing the right data source, review polypharmacy challenges and using EHRs for MLTC research. We summarise how linking EHRs can bring a more complete picture of patient health, for which coding drug and clinical data appropriately is key. We also summarise data models which can contribute to standardisation. We end with a larger section on 'Code list tools, methods, and resources' 5 which cover existing resources to build code lists, existing code lists to access, and methodological best practices for code lists now and in the future.

2. Challenges in defining multiple long-term conditions

The challenge of forming a concise definition encapsulating the nature of the diseases, organ systems affected and epidemiological characteristics, whilst being reflective of patient experience, complicates the process of standardising research outputs aiming to address MLTC symptoms and burdenomeness. [1, 14]

The literature shows inconsistency in the characterisation of MLTCs [15, 16]. A study found 36.4% of 566 studies did not report a reference definition for MLTCs, 12.9% did not include the list of conditions chosen for their measure and 79.9% reported types of condition within single measures (respiratory conditions vs. asthma) with high variability in the number of conditions included (2-285)[15]. The majority of these studies (74%) [17] are subject to at least moderate risk of condition selection bias in terms of their inclusion and exclusion criteria. For example, there is a noticeable under-representation of mental health conditions, which are essential for a

comprehensive understanding of the characteristics of MLTCs, as mental and physical health have a combined effect on clinical outcomes, quality of life, mortality and initiative in personal health management [17, 18, 19, 20, 21].

Guidance on consistent MLTC measurement for reproducible and standardised research is offered by several studies [17, 22]. Although there is variability and lack of comparability in existing characterisations, studies similarly focus on conditions with higher prevalence and severe impact[23]. Characterisation of MLTCs using universally accepted measures and agreed list of conditions is necessary for valid and repeatable data analyses and streamlined aggregation across studies, leading to optimal patient outcomes. Below we outline some of the key questions and considerations that influence the creation of a standardised list of conditions:

- There is a lack of consensus on categorisation of LTCs, highlighted well in the Delphi study by Ho et al.[15]:
 - Should a list include broad categories of disease or count individual diseases separately (even though they may share a similar pathophysiological process)? For example, cardiovascular disease as a broad category or ischaemic heart disease (IHD) and cerebrovascular disease separately [15, 24].
 - Should a list include risk factors on the causal pathway to other conditions? For example, including both hypertension and IHD, where hypertension is a risk factor for IHD [15, 24].
- For weighted measures carefully consider: inclusion of acute conditions in addition to chronic, treatment of conditions that follow a relapsing-remitting course, and wider societal and lifestyle factors with predictive capacity for clinical outcomes[25, 26, 27].
- Consider validity of weighted measures for severity of condition against MLTC populations. Within MLTC, conditions can interact and amplify each other. The combined impact may be more complex than merely adding up individual illnesses. Clusters of conditions can have a synergistic effect on functional ability, with specific diseases influencing a patient’s life in unique ways. This complexity is not adequately captured by simple counts or combination-based indices.

- Generalisability of measures by validating new or existing measures against multiple healthcare outcomes and representative population groups.[28]
- Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement - there can be a gap between observed health recording of MLTC severity and the self-reported MLTC burdensomeness [23]. A unified approach to raise understanding between healthcare practitioners and patients can lessen this gap.
- Coding of drugs is less subjective than diagnosis or symptom data due to electronic prescribing embedded within clinical systems, i.e. the presence of a particular drug code indicates prescription of the exact preparation on the specified date. However, we cannot be sure the patient took the drug prescribed, and prescribing via hospital outpatients is not recorded in GPs.

People living with MLTCs also experience higher rates of polypharmacy (prescribing or taking more drugs than are required [29]) and are subject to adverse drug events (ADRs), unplanned hospitalisations and overprescribing [30, 10]. Optimising polypharmacy decision making is thus necessary to avoid the above experiences and ensure there is more benefit than harm when an individual takes a combination of drugs. Having a patient-centered approach with a holistic view of MLTCs and their situational or social contexts [31], over an individual condition focus, plays a vital role in this area [8, 14].

3. Why are data sources important: using EHRs for MLTC research

The data source selected has a considerable impact on the validity of a research study. Johnston’s findings on common data sources were found to include a mixture of administrative ‘coded’ databases, EHRs, patient self-report and clinical examinations. Although no recommendations were found of a data source for MLTC measures specifically, choice of data source were shown to affect measured MLTC prevalence and burden [16].

A cross-sectional study comparing MLTC prevalence in the general population to prevalence in primary care practices, estimated a difference of 10%. Understandably, the study suggests the suitability of a data source to be dependent on use case [32]. For example, prevalence estimates of MLTC and

disease burdensomeness were both higher in the clinical setting. Although the population subset attending in clinic can be more informative for resource allocation, costs and overall burden to healthcare professionals, integrating other data sources can increase understanding of self-reported disease burden and representation of disease in the general population.

Some studies indicate preference for EHRs due to data completeness but state impracticality in larger studies, making administrative data ultimately favourable [33, 34]. Although coded administrative data can be preferable for ease of use in larger studies, it can be limited due to data quality and lack of standardisation in quality assessments [33, 35]. Some patient information is recorded in unstructured free text with no formal coding such as mental health [35], and new codes are being developed in deprecated coding systems such as Read Codes [36]; omitting this data in downstream analysis could bias results if important patient information is only recorded in free text, and if sub-samples during cohort selection are omitted due to missing or legacy codes. Data access, time restrictions, availability of data and resources, and lack of standardisation further complicates and limits the decision making process for data source selection [16].

All of these points factor into the challenge and complexities of undertaking MLTC research; a researcher must assess completeness, accuracy and quality of the measures and outcomes derived from the selected data source, keeping feasibility in mind.

In a broader sense, EHRs have become increasingly popular for healthcare research. This increased uptake comes with valid concerns about the inclusion of potentially erroneous, miscoded and missing data, and how this could limit or invalidate health findings leading to unsound public health policies [2, 37].

Challenges related to using EHRs for healthcare research:

- Data is subject to selection, measurement and confounding bias - treatment and exposure is not assigned randomly [2].
- Lack of EHR interoperability due to differences in data structure, data model and software systems, can make it difficult harmonise across data sources [2].
- Use of different coding systems. Unique identifiers are not commonly transferable across data sources; even when using well-known external

coding systems, their usage can vary across sources and change over time [38].

- Coding incompleteness and missing codes can make it difficult to query and extract relevant subsets of data, making it a cyclic process between development of code sets and term sets, and requiring manual review by clinical experts throughout the process of curating lists.
- Some systems use abbreviations or similar terminology for clinically distinct concepts. An example given by Hoffman et al., 'MS' could mean 'mitral stenosis', 'multiple sclerosis' and 'morphine sulphate'. Contextual information or coding may help bring clarity [2].
- Extraction of clinically meaningful features from the raw dataset, and the large variation in coding practices between clinicians [39].
- Using unstructured and multimodal data to capture semantic relationships and improve predictive accuracy is challenging, especially with non standardised clinical notes (unordered or illegible). Pre-processing multi-modal data for model input and reviewing free text manually can be time consuming and costly [40], yet information can be lost when extracting meaningful patient features from structured data, or one single modality [41, 42, 43].

Quality issues in EHRs including information incompleteness, inaccuracy and inconsistency [44], will effect the validity of any secondary use-cases of EHRs, such as artificial intelligence (AI) applications. Thus, papers specifically assessing data quality, accuracy and representativeness are particularly important [45, 46, 47, 48, 49] for evaluating the appropriateness of a data source for an intended use case. Understanding the shortcomings may also provide opportunity to feedback for improvement at source of data generation.

Extracting, loading and restructuring health datasets into a research-ready format can be challenging due to the size of the data, lack of detailed metadata, and insufficient documentation on prior data processing steps (particularly relevant for secondary data sources such as EHRs). Collaboration between those with clinical expertise and data wrangling expertise is essential to ensure both domain knowledge and data best practices.

4. Potential improvements and solutions

We have covered background and challenges related to using EHR data to study MLTCs and how to appropriately code drug and clinical data into lists for research applications. In this next section, we shift focus onto practical improvements and solutions for these processes.

4.1. *Linking electronic health records*

Linked EHRs can be used to get a better picture of patient health, expand the wealth of information available for public health researchers and curate evidence to guide health policies and services [50, 51]. However, challenges in preserving data security and anonymity of EHRs present a significant barrier to data linkage.

There are data providers currently providing linked EHR subsets of the population, for example CPRD (Clinical Practice Research Datalink) [52], Oxford-RCGP [53], QResearch [54], OpenSafely [55] and SAIL Databank [56]. Supplementary table 9 provided in the study by Wood et al. (2021) provides more detail on these resources, population covered, data linkage, data security and code sharing [57].

Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, there was no access to national linked EHRs across England [57]. The CVD-COVID-UK partnership, originally launched to support understanding of COVID-19 associated prognosis and outcomes, aims to provide deidentified, linked EHRs for the UK population within a secure environment [57].

A Trusted Research Environment (TRE) is a secure environment, essential for preservation of patient privacy. The NHS Digital TRE includes primary care data, Hospital Episode Statistics (HES), death registry, COVID-19 laboratory tests and community dispensed medications, with intention to add specialist intensive care and hospital electronic prescribing. This linked cohort includes more than 96% of the English population, emphasising the importance of person level data linkage for completeness of key characteristics [57].

Unfortunately the linkage process is prone to linkage error, further compounded by processes being performed by different agencies and fragmented information available about the data processing before, during and after linkage [51].

To assist the process, The STROBE and RECORD statements [58, 59] include guidelines on reporting to understand the linkage process, whilst the

GUILD guidance aims to inform data users on how to assess potential sources of linkage error [51].

In line with the guidelines enabling best practices above, CPRD and NHS Digital have published an open access report [50] detailing their linkage methodology. The aim is to support data users by providing necessary information to make informed decisions on research study design and respective analyses [50].

As linkage is increasingly being used to create a more complete picture for research, policy and resource allocation, detailed sharing of the linkage methodology can improve transparency and increase reproducibility [60, 61]. This facilitates a better understanding of how to curate and interpret studies using linked data and how to address relevant systemic biases[62] or linkage errors downstream[51].

4.2. Practices in coding drug and clinical data

Clinical terminologies have become increasingly recognised as being key resources for knowledge management and data integration [63]. With the increasing complexities of health disciplines and respective data being collected, terminologies can make EHRs more manageable in clinical practice and research [64].

Transforming clinical codes to well defined and standardised terminology is required to improve quality, transferability, linkage and data retrieval due to mapped structural and hierarchical attributes of EHR data[3] , though there is potential for loss in data fidelity [65]. There is also ease in adopting terminology models to new software systems, with minimal understanding of coding system required, by healthcare domain experts [66]. However, the primary use of EHR is by time-pressured clinicians and administrative staff to document individual patient encounters with many important demands on their focus. Whilst standardisation of coding practices is ideal, behaviour change in healthcare practice is challenging [67]. Education and training, financial incentives and systemic changes to EHR systems are potential solutions. [67, 68].

Code lists are a practical way to support creating transferable data queries and extract patient cohorts or variables of interests. They also increase interoperability by facilitating easier data linkage from sources with different data structures, models and processing methods [69].

However, the methodology for code list generation is rarely transparent, well documented and publicly available. Some of the approaches to ensure

validity of code lists have been included in our subsection 'Methodology best practices for code lists' 5.1.

Coding systems assign identifiers for classification of clinical concepts. Desirable traits for these systems include having a meaningful structure and uniqueness for clinical terms and drugs. This may not always be possible depending on the level of complexity of the coding system.

Furthermore, to understand and measure diseases with tools allowing efficient and methodical storing, comparison and analysis over time is essential to having a well defined coding system.

Some of the common clinical and drug coding terminologies and systems used as sources for knowledge management, data interoperability and decision support [70] include SNOMED CT (and dm+d) [71], BNF (British National Formulary)[72, 73], ATC (Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical) Classification System [74], ICD-11 [75] and Read (v2,v3) codes [66].

Coding systems such as Read, have been superseded by SNOMED CT, and depending on the nature of the record and location (England, Scotland & Wales), either coding systems may be preferable or in a state of transition. Mapping files are released by NHS BSA on a monthly basis to assist with mapping between these coding systems. These can be used for a more comprehensive code mapping and classification in clinical code lists [76]. However, terms are not necessarily mapped to a corresponding code, creating a separate challenge requiring classification of free text terms.

All coding systems aim to have clear standards with their own prioritised requirements, interoperability, and unique level of granularity whilst maintaining semantic interoperability. The challenge is maintaining a balance of all these requirements over time and allowing mapping between the various systems. Resources and suggested best practices on building code lists across systems, as well as openly available tools and repositories, will be covered in 'Potential solutions: Tools, methods and resources'.

4.3. Using data models for more structure

Data models have become increasingly popular with increased data accessibility, data modalities and linkage possibilities, but are not without practical limitations. Multimodal datasets with different metadata and terminology coding make merging datasets more challenging [77, 78].

Data models have been used to structure and standardise observational databases into a common format. Subsequently, this makes data linkage

between datasets conforming to the same data models more efficient. However, manual mapping of concepts and terminology is one of the most time-consuming tasks when using data models [79].

There are several common data models available; a comprehensive comparison can be found in Garza’s review [80], evaluating four Common Data Models (CDMs) to structure health data: OMOP (Observational Medical Outcome Partnership)[81], Sentinel[82], PCORnet [83] and CDISC SDTM [84]. As the review concludes OMOP CDM best meets the criteria for supporting data sharing from EHR based studies [80], this is what we decided to focused on.

The studies evaluating the process of implementing OMOP’s CDM on UK’s EHR data sources, include IMRD (IQVIA Medical Research Data - previously known as THIN), CPRD and more recently UK Biobank with linkage to HES and ONS [85, 86, 77]. Prior to this, literature includes validating OMOP’s CDM in representing 10 observational health databases in the US, for drug safety surveillance [87].

In general, there are clear benefits in having a common data model, including workflow autonomy (ability for a multi-disciplinary team to independently work on data workflows with minimised barriers) and increased collaboration on complex datasets with standardised terminology and modelling, mitigating requirement of relevant expertise for interpretation of each data attribute [87]. CDM implementation increases efficiency in analyses through parallel querying, and facilitates use of a decentralized network of data (data access is limited to summarized data), maximising patient data privacy [77].

Studies suggest demographic characteristics, risk factors and comorbidities are mapped with consistency to the CDM and demonstrate their potential to be used in harmonizing large, complex datasets [77, 86, 85].

Limitations however are also present. These include semantically unmapped or incomplete diagnostic, laboratory and drug codes [85, 77] causing discrepancy in patients identified with comorbidity in true data and CDM transformed data, restrictions imposed by the ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) process (diagnostic codes outside observation period), and limitations in integrating certain data types (including genomic and questionnaire data) [86]. As an example, 25% of medical and 55% of drug codes in raw IMRD database were not listed in the OMOP terminology dictionary, representing 6 % condition occurrence counts, 4 % procedure occurrence counts and 7 % drug exposure counts. [77] On a related topic, DExtER, ‘Data extrac-

tion for epidemiological research’,[88, 89] is a tool created with a framework designed to address some of the limitations in using EHRs from multiple data sources in MLTC research, specifically in primary care, with the aim to expand application to linked and international datasets [89].

Further work required to evaluate tools which address the challenges outlined above. This includes high quality and complete mapping for primary care drug prescriptions and laboratory results, minimizing risk of diversions in CDM versions over time [77, 85] and compatibility with bespoke data sources using local coding systems and the ability to explicitly capture missingness [86].

5. Code list tools, methods and resources

As outlined in ‘Potential improvements: Practices in coding drug and clinical data’ 4.2, code lists are a great way to categorise and code relevant clinical information to enable efficient retrieval from data sources at a later stage. This section has been included to support the process of filtering records in MLTC studies, prioritising reusability, standardised methodology and transparency. Table 1 provides a list of tools, resources and repositories to supplement this process. We have chosen to exclude internal code list builder tools provided by data providers such as CPRD and SAIL for their respective data dictionaries, as these are not open to public.

Table 1: Tools and resources for building code lists. If the entry includes a tool to assist curating and processing of code lists it is marked with **T**. If the entry is a resource or repository (for example, containing pre-existing code lists), it is marked with **R**. For open access, we mark with **OA**, and in the case of decommissioned, **D**.

Name	Description	Categories
Snomedizer (R package)[90]	Interface for SNOMED CT Browser. Maintains structure of clinical concepts and can be used to write concise queries using Expression Constraint Language; deriving linked child concepts can effectively determine generic drug names. Legally prescribed drugs and brand names can be US specific. The methodology and drug lists are hosted on the AIM-RSF GitHub [91].	T, OA
wardle GitHub repository[92]	Implements the UK NHS dm+d extension. Provides tools built around SNOMED CT, with support to analyse expressions and concepts, and cross-mapping code terminologies. Can access drug terminology including brand names, as implemented in code lists hosted on the AIM-RSF GitHub[91].	T, OA
Open-Prescribing[93]	OpenSAFELY tool using normalised data to research trends in England’s NHS primary care prescribing data, using drug terms or BNF hierarchical structure.	T, OA
RxNorm[94]	Database of normalized names for generic and brand drugs for clinical drug terminology in the US, and a tool to support semantic interoperability between drug terminologies and pharmacy knowledge base systems.	T, OA
SNOWSTORM [95]	SNOMED CT terminology server using elastic search. Includes multi-lingual search and content retrieval. Uses concept and description based search methods, with optional constraints to limit scope of search.	T, OA

OpenCodelists [96]	Large repository hosted by OpenSAFELY for creating and sharing code lists, including PseudoBNF, CTV3 (Read V3), ICD-10 and SNOMED CT. Users must query each coding system individually, providing a single search term. Inclusion and exclusion criteria functionality integrated.	T, R, OA
Dexter Phenotype Library	a phenotype code list management tool in the Dexter ecosystem [88, 89].	T, R
GetSet	From paper by Williams et al. [64], is a term set tool allowing users to create and verify term sets, although this is no longer actively maintained.	T, OA, D
SNOMED CT Browser & dm+d extension[97]	Comprehensive global healthcare terminology server, with an extension dictionary for medicines and devices. Recommended by the NHS for validated and consistent representation of clinical content which maps to international standards.	R, OA
British National Formulary (BNF)[98]	Information on the selection, prescribing and administration of medicines. Treatment summaries outline drug use related to a particular body system, or treatments for common conditions. For each drug, licensed brand names are listed.	R, OA
HDR UK Phenotype Library[99]	For each phenotype the metadata, implementation methodology and code is included in existing collections from national research initiatives. These include BREATHE (respiratory phenotypes collated by the HDR UK Hub for Respiratory Health), ClinicalCodes [100]), British Heart Foundation (BHF) Data Science Centre amongst others. The library aims to be a centralised repository for code lists, dissemination of tools and algorithms with the aim of increasing research reproducibility and transparency. does not aim to standardize or harmonise disease definitions. This becomes a challenge when aiming to combine studies from different data sources.	R, OA

Primary Care Domain Reference Set Portal	Resource for analysis of any condition covered in the Quality and Outcomes Framework (QOF) business rulesets. QOF financially incentivises GP practices to keep accurate patient registers for chronic diseases, with established code lists to define these conditions and disease monitoring processes [101].	R, OA
NHS Digital Clusters	Repository containing cluster categories for clinical and drug codes, specifically SNOMED [102].	R, OA
CPRD @ Cambridge Code Lists [103, 104]	Covers databases Gold and Aurum. Contains condition lists, with Aurum methodology work in progress on last visit [09/2023].	R, OA
THINKING Group [105]	GitHub repository contains medical condition and drug lists created using the Dexter Phenotype Library [88, 89]	R, OA
AIM-RSF drug-lists [91]	GitHub repository, contains drug lists with methodology documentation created using the Dexter Phenotype Library [88] in collaboration with THINKINGGroup [105].	R, OA

5.1. Methodology best practices for code lists

Best practice guidelines can ensure some degree of validity and confidence in any research decisions made for cohort selection methodology. It is not common practice to share these methodologies. As a case study for this paper, we will focus on the methodology used by the AIM-RSF. The methodology for the code list generation is stored within a GitHub repository[91] and outlined in Figure 1. It relies on the snomedizer package [90], dm+d server implementation [92] and Dexter Phenotype Library tool which filters relevant codes based on input inclusion and exclusion term sets.

Figure 1: Methodology to curate drug lists. A. Drug concepts are curated by a clinician, consisting of drug names or substances. B. Snomedizer takes A as input; the `concept_find()` function finds all child drug terms and concept IDs related to input A. C. The server endpoint [90] does not cover brand names for medications prescribed in the UK. The dm+d library [92] is therefore used to retrieve associated brand names. D. Prepare input for Dexter Phenotype Library [88] (step E), the output from C is processed to remove duplicates and redundant information, and the JSON file is converted into a flat file. E. The drug terms from the flat file are used as input to Dexter Phenotype Library, which builds a SQL query to filter and retrieve all term matches from data dictionaries. This includes database specific identifiers, and drug codes available in respective dictionaries. For example, UK BioBank, dm+d, ATC codes. The output can then be reviewed by clinician to remove unrelated codes, and validate those remaining. *ECL = Expression Constraint Language*

These are best practices recommended and implemented in our drug

lists[91]:

1. Reviewing repositories for pre-existing lists in an effort to standardise and reuse code lists where possible.
2. Establishing consensus approach with the research team on categorization of phenotypes. Some methods include use of BNF, Read and SNOMED hierarchy with a condition treatment focus. Others may use a substance based approach, anatomical therapeutic effects or use of other terminology model structures to group concepts and will be largely dependent on individuals use case.
3. Search strategy - curating term sets for explicit inclusions and exclusions for phenotype or drug. Evaluating representativeness (is the code set representative of the condition?), sensitivity and specificity (the degree to which a code set correctly identifies patients with a particular condition [106]) and possibility of unintentional inclusions in output during search.
4. Handling duplicate term appearances, multi-use drugs, combination drugs. In case of drug lists, determine handling of drugs with multiple appearances in model hierarchy (if terminology does not support multiple inheritance, codes for a condition will appear in separate branches requiring an exhaustive term search) and duplicate codes (some coding systems including SNOMED CT allow coding in multiple ways for the same concept [106]).
5. Consideration of covariate codes - inclusion of codes which may indicate a diagnosis, in the absence of a diagnosis code. For example, considering codes for 'hypertension annual review' in the absence of a 'hypertension' diagnosis code [106].
6. Considering synonyms, in cases which there are multiple descriptions encoding the same concept[106]. Table 2 illustrates the large variation in terms retrieved for different drug classes using generic and brand drug names as input query.
7. Implementing clinical expert review of condition or drug lists, for validity, sensitivity and representativeness.
8. Mapping of coding systems and populating missing codes as best as possible - using BNF to SNOMED mapping, string matching algorithms such as fuzzy search, Levenshtein distance, to map term sets to code sets, or natural language processing to tag constituent parts of drug and predict respective codes.[76] Figure 2 illustrates the large

number of missing BNF and ATC codes with respect to the total terms retrieved for 15 drug classes, combined from five different data sources.

9. Adaptability and semantic interoperability - considering how easily code lists can be updated. Thus, including term sets with code lists is recommended to allow effortless interpretability and functionality to adapt lists to include new codes.
10. FAIR research principles - Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR). FAIR practices allow users to openly critique and understand the decision making process when creating code lists: term inclusions/exclusions, manual modifications with clear justification; version control for reproducibility and reusability; clinical expert review; stating data sources.
11. Use of existing guidelines for study design and use of AI [59, 58, 107].

Table 2: Drug code list query totals for brand names, generic and combined totals. Terms retrieved refer to the terms returned by databases when using all query terms in search, with versioning referring to number of iterations for clinical validation required for each code list. See Figure 1 for code list methodology. *MAOI*=*Monoamine Oxidase Inhibitors*, *SNRI*=*Serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors*, *AD*=*Antidepressants*.

Drug List Counts					
Code list	Generic Query	Brand Query	Total Count	Terms Retrieved	Versions
Anticonvulsants	0	137	137	9695	2
Antipsychotics	24	64	88	6150	2
Benzodiazepines	14	25	39	3679	2
Dementia	4	28	32	1476	1
Galantamine	1	12	13	332	1
Lithium	1	9	10	232	2
Metformin	20	21	41	958	2
Mirtazapine	1	1	2	582	1
MAOI	4	0	4	78	2
Rivastigmine	1	11	12	483	1

SNRI	5	36	41	1062	2
Strong Opioids	16	116	132	6739	3
Tricyclic AD	12	25	37	2596	2
Weak Opioids	3	55	58	3430	2

Figure 2: Comparing missing code counts for BNF and ATC against the total number of corresponding term counts for each drug class, showing the large number of missing codes in data sources for both coding systems. This has been combined for terms extracted from the following data sources: CEGEDIM, CPRD Gold, CPRD Aurum UHB, IMRD. See Figure 1 for code list methodology *MAOI*=Monoamine Oxidase Inhibitors, *SNRI*=Serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors, *AD*=Antidepressants

5.2. Legacy of clinical coding

Although legacy coding systems come with individual challenges which require their own consideration, the progressive development of multiple coding systems can be tackled by having a tool which has functionality to map

between coding systems. Code mapping files [76] can be used as initial reference for this process. Natural language processing methods to capture constituent parts of drug terms (substance, dosage strength, administration route, brand name) and mapping to corresponding codes can be used to incorporate free unstructured text, synonyms and handling erroneous values. Having flexibility to adapt to new or unstructured terms can be ideal in case of new codes or descriptions being released, otherwise requiring manual review.

Code lists and methodology to date stored in a shared repository would allow reproducibility and transferability across MLTC studies using multiple data sources. Clinical validation would however still be required to examine transferability of coding algorithms and representativeness of condition or treatment across code lists for specific data dictionaries.

Work to establish boundaries and overlap between code list terms could be done using language models tuned on health data to identify contextual similarities between term sets and identify outliers visually, assisting the validation process.

6. Conclusions

Adoption of the SNOMED CT model across healthcare systems is a great step towards having a unified approach in structuring and coding clinical information in a useful manner, although at a national level the transition from legacy systems will take time. Alongside a tool for challenges relating to legacy coding systems, the best practices outlined above with a repository collating all code lists and resources will benefit researchers in developing MLTC cohorts.

The transition of EHRs being used for research as opposed to primarily for clinical observation has shifted the focus to improving data quality and standards. There are active initiatives specifically dedicated to improving MLTC research challenges and engaging multi-disciplinary communities, as well as recent best practice guidelines focusing on these topics. For example, a recent paper[108] includes guidance on best practices in developing code lists, providing a 9-step checklist based on a literature search and workshop. This complimentary paper, with similar goals to ours, highlights the growing acknowledgment that clear standards and best practice guidelines are seen as a solution to some of the challenges that this research area faces.

Facilitating collaborative and transparent MLTC research is essential to its future direction; we hope the challenges and solutions outlined in this paper, and others like it, can be implemented by researchers to improve research quality, as well as encourage researchers to build on these familiar concepts to improve the future landscape of MLTC research.

7. List of Abbreviations

ADR	adverse drug event	FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
AI	Artificial Intelligence	HES	Hospital Episode Statistics
AIM	AI for Multiple Long-term Conditions	IMRD	IQVIA Medical Research Data
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (Classification System)	LTC	Long-Term Condition
BNF	British National Formulary	MLTC	Multiple Long-Term Conditions
BHF	British Heart Foundation	OMOP	Observational Medical Outcome Partnership
CDM	Common Data Model	RSF	Research Support Facility
CPRD	Clinical Practice Research Datalink	SMR	Structured Medication Review
EHR	Electronic Health Record	TRE	Trusted Research Environment
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load	QOF	Quality and Outcomes Framework

Table 3: List of abbreviations

8. Declarations

8.1. Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

Not applicable

8.2. Consent for Publication

Not applicable

8.3. Availability of Data and Materials

The datasets analysed during the current study are available in the AIM-RSF drug-lists repository, <https://github.com/aim-rsf/drug-lists>.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10816326> [91]

8.4. Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests

8.5. Funding

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8.6. Authors' Contributions

MM contributed to initial draft, major revisions, curation and interpretation of data. RS was a major contributor to substantive revisions of draft, interpretation of data and conceptualization of work. JC contributed to revisions of paper, curation and all clinical validation of data. AMM contributed to conceptualization and design of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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